

Clinical study of otomycosis in patients with diabetes mellitus

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Abstract :

Background:

Otomycosis is a fungal infection of the external auditory canal, middle ear, and open mastoid cavity, often found in ENT OPD. It is more common in immunocompromised patients, such as diabetes mellitus, AIDS, and on immunosuppressants, and can complicate clinical presentations and treatment outcomes.

Objective of the study:

To study the commonest mode of presentation, predisposing factors and fungal profile in otomycosis patients with diabetes mellitus.

Material and Methods:

A descriptive cross sectional study was conducted among 50 Patients attending ENT Op who are clinically diagnosed with otomycosis were screened for diabetes mellitus. Patients already with diabetes and who are newly diagnosed with diabetes mellitus were also included in the study. Examination of the external ear canal, tympanic membrane and middle ear was done by otoscope. Materials from external auditory canal was taken using sterile swab and sent to the microbiology lab for processing and to know the fungal growth pattern.

Results:

The median age of 51.50 years (IQR: 17.5) and 54% of patients with otomycosis report itching as the primary symptom. Around 52% of patients reported manipulation of the ear canal as a predisposing factor and 4% of patients identified swimming as a contributing factor. The most frequently isolated fungus was *Aspergillus niger*, accounting for 44% of cases followed by *Aspergillus flavus* comprising 32% of cases, *Aspergillus fumigatus* identified in 16% of cases, *Candida krusei* representing 4% of isolates, *scedosporiumapiospermum* isolated in 2% of cases and *Scedosporiumproliferans* also representing 2%, similar to *Scedosporiumapiospermum*.

Conclusion: Although *Candida krusei* and *Scedosporium* are present, their detection is crucial to prevent outbreaks. Further research is needed to understand environmental factors contributing to *Aspergillus* species' high prevalence and their antifungal resistance patterns. *Candida krusei* and *Scedosporium* growth were present, their detection which is rare is crucial to know their prevalence and treatment with resistance pattern. Further research is needed to understand environmental factors contributing to *Aspergillus* species' high prevalence and their antifungal resistance patterns.

Key words: *Otomycosis, Diabetes Mellitus fungal infection & Aspergillus*

Introduction:

Otomycosis is a fungal infection of the external auditory canal, middle ear and open mastoid cavity which are frequently encountered in ENT OPD. The predisposing factors are habitual instrumentation, swimming, use of antibiotics, unhygienic habits and hearing aid usage.⁽¹⁾ The symptoms of otomycosis includes itching, otalgia, otorrhoea, aural fullness, ear block, and tinnitus.⁽²⁾ The prevalence of otomycosis varies globally, with estimates ranging from 9% to 30%, and it is more common in warm, humid climates where fungi thrive. The most common fungal organisms causing otomycosis are *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus fumigatus*, *Candida albicans* and *Candida tropicalis*.⁽³⁾ Otomycosis is seen more frequently in immunocompromised patients as compared to immunocompetent patients.⁽¹⁾ Patients with diabetes mellitus, AIDS and patients on immunosuppressants or receiving chemotherapy are

more commonly susceptible to otomycosis and are at risk of potential complications of otomycosis.^(1, 2)

Diabetes mellitus has been identified as a notable risk factor for otomycosis due to its immunocompromising effects, which can predispose patients to opportunistic infections. The interaction between diabetes and fungal infections can complicate clinical presentations and treatment outcomes. Invasive fungal infections of the ear, such as invasive fungal otitis media, malignant otitis externa have been reported in diabetic patients, highlighting the need for heightened clinical awareness and prompt intervention.⁽⁴⁾In this study we will describe the commonest presentation, predisposing factors, the spectrum of fungi of otomycosis in patients with diabetes mellitus.

Fungal infections are also closely associated with cases of CSOM because fungi thrive in moist environment, but many authors have focused their attention on the bacterial flora, and little is known about the mycological aspects of these, the importance of which has grown in recent years due to the overuse of broad spectrum antibiotics, corticosteroids, and cytotoxic chemotherapy, as well as an increase in the number of immune deficiency disorders.⁽⁵⁾The most prevalent fungus are *Aspergillus* and *Candida* spp. Chronic ear discharge is a significant factor in the development of fungal infection in otitis media. It generates a humid situation in the ear and shifts the pH to alkaline. Epithelial debris promotes the development of fungus.⁽⁶⁾

Objective of the study:

To study the commonest mode of presentation, predisposing factors and fungal profile in otomycosis patients with diabetes mellitus.

Material and methods:

Study Setting:

The study was conducted in Otorhinolaryngology Department of Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre.

Study duration:

One Year.

Study design:

Descriptive cross sectional study

Sample size:

Fifty cases (based on the earlier hospital records average 3 cases per month underwent treatment for same complaint of otomycosis in diabetes mellitus) were included in the study.

Study Participants:

The study participants included were Patients attending Otorhinolaryngology department of Trichy SRM Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, fulfilling the inclusion criteria.

Inclusion criteria:

- Patients from 15 years of age
- Clinically diagnosed to have otomycosis with diabetes mellitus.

Exclusion criteria:

- Without diabetes mellitus
- Other immunocompromised status
 - HIV,
 - Post organ transplant
 - Patients on radiotherapy/chemotherapy
 - Patients on any immunosuppressant therapy

Sampling Method:

As per convenient sampling patients those who fulfilling the inclusion criteria with consent were taken into the study.

Methodology

Data collection was done by principal investigator (Post graduate in otorhinolaryngology) using structured proforma. An Informed and written consent was obtained in their own understanding from all the subjects prior to their participation in the study. Patients attending ENT Op who are clinically diagnosed with otomycosis were screened for diabetes mellitus. Patients already with diabetes and who are newly diagnosed with diabetes mellitus were also included in our study as per the inclusion and exclusion criteria. Examination of the external ear canal, tympanic membrane and middle ear was done by otoscope and otoendoscopy. Materials from external auditory canal was scooped out and sent in a sterile container without adding any preservative to the microbiology lab for processing and to know the fungi growth pattern.

Figure 1:Otoendoscopic image of otomycosis

Figure 2: Colony morphology of *Aspergillus niger* in Sabaroud dextrose agar.

Figure 3: Microscopic appearance of *Aspergillus fumigatus* (Lactophenol cotton blue stain)

Figure 4: Microscopic appearance of *Aspergillus niger* (Lactophenol cotton blue stain)

Statistical analysis

The collected study data were entered in Microsoft Office Excel 2013 and analysed using SPSS 21 software. Continuous variables follows normal distribution was expressed as mean and Standard Deviation. Description of categorical variables was expressed as frequency and Percentage.

Ethical consideration

Ethical principles such as respect to the patient, beneficence and justice were strictly adhered. Ethical committee approval was obtained before starting the study. The approval to conduct the present study was obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee. Confidentiality of the study participants was maintained throughout the study.

Results

Table 1: Basic characteristic among otomycosis patients with diabetes mellitus

	Frequency	Percent
Age category		
40 to 50 years	24	48.0%
> 50 to 60 years	10	20.0%
> 60 to 70 years	11	22.0%
> 70 years	5	10.0%
Mean ± SD	55.22 ± 10.79	
Median [IQR]	51.50 [17.5]	
Gender		
Male	21	42%
Female	29	58%
Laterality		
Bilateral	1	2.0%
Left	18	36.0%
Right	31	62.0%
Intact Tympanic membrane	50	100%
CSOM	0	0%
Total	50	100.0%

The majority of the study participants within the 40 to 50 years age group, representing 48.0% of the population. This is followed by 22.0% in the 60 to 70 yearsage category and 20.0% in the 50 to 60 yearsage group. A smaller proportion (10.0%) are above 70 years. The median age of 51.50 years (IQR: 17.5) suggests a relatively younger cohort. The gender distribution shows a higher proportion of females (58%) compared to males (42%), In terms of laterality, (62%) of the cases are right-sided, while (36%) affect the left side, with only (2%) being

bilateral. This skew toward unilateral involvement, particularly on the left side. The tympanic membrane was intact for all the cases, and chronic suppurative otitis media (CSOM) was not observed in any of the cases.

Figure 5: Symptoms distribution among otomycosis patients with diabetes mellitus

The figure 5 shows (34%) of patients with otomycosis report itching as the primary symptom. Followed by (25%) of patients reported otalgia, (22%) of patients reported ear blockage and (19%) of patients presented with discharge from the ear.

Table 2: Predisposing factors for otomycosis patients with diabetes mellitus

Predisposing factors	N	%
Manipulation	26	52%
Swimming	2	4%
Antibiotic usage	0	0%
Trauma	0	0%
Total	50	100%

Note: Multiple response question.

Table 2 shows predisposing factors for otomycosis among diabetic patients. Around 52% of patients reported manipulation of the ear canal as a predisposing factor and 4% of patients identified swimming as a contributing factor

Figure 2: Simple bar diagram shows various fungal isolates in study population

Figure 2 shows the most frequently isolated fungus was *Aspergillus niger*, accounting for 44% of cases. The second most common isolate was *Aspergillus flavus* comprising 32% of cases followed by *Aspergillus fumigatus* identified in 16% of cases, *Candida krusei* representing 4% of

isolates, *Scedosporium apiospermum* isolated in 2% of cases and *Scedosporium proliferans* also representing 2%, similar to *Scedosporium apiospermum*.

Discussion:

The majority of the otomycosis patients with diabetes mellitus fall in the 40 to 50 years category (48.0%), followed by 22.0% in the 60 to 70 years range. A smaller proportion (10%) is over 70 years. This age distribution highlights that middle-aged to older adults with diabetes are more susceptible to otomycosis. For instance, a study done by Prasad Sc et al⁽⁷⁾ and BojanovićM et al⁽⁸⁾ in the Indian subcontinent indicated that younger populations are also affected, but the prevalence increases with age, particularly in diabetic patients who may have compromised immune systems, making them more susceptible to infections like otomycosis. Diabetes mellitus, especially poorly controlled, compromises immune function and creates an environment conducive to fungal infections like otomycosis, particularly in older age groups where immunity may be further diminished. The median age of 51.50 years (IQR: 17.5) further emphasize that this condition disproportionately affects patients in the latter half of life, when chronic complications of diabetes, including fungal infections, tend to manifest. The gender ratio of the present study indicated a higher prevalence of otomycosis in females (58%) compared to males (42%). This gender discrepancy may reflect different exposure levels to risk factors such as swimming or hygiene practices prevalent in different groups. A significant proportion of patients exhibit right-sided otomycosis (62%), with 36% experiencing left-sided infection, and 2% showing bilateral involvement. The Gohar MS et al⁽⁹⁾ reported bilateral disease in only 20% of patients, indicating that unilateral infections are more common across different populations. This finding is consistent with other studies that show a tendency for unilateral presentations in otomycosis cases. This asymmetry in otomycosis could be attributed to individual behaviors or anatomical factors such as handedness influencing ear cleaning habits or environmental exposures. For diabetic patients, who are already prone to slow healing and secondary infections, understanding which side is more frequently affected can help in clinical decision-making, particularly in addressing recurrent infections or complications like tympanic membrane perforation or invasive fungal infections. Otomycosis in patients with diabetes presents unique challenges due to their immunocompromised state and higher risk of complications. Diabetic patients are more prone to chronic, recurrent otomycosis, and aggressive management with

antifungals, regular cleaning of the ear canal, and glycemic control is crucial. The higher proportion of left-sided infections may indicate specific patient behaviors or ear cleaning practices that can be modified to reduce recurrence.

In diabetic patients, otomycosis tends to present with a combination of pruritus (itching), otalgia, discharge, and ear blockage, which may be more severe and recurrent due to their underlying condition. Regular ear debridement, topical antifungal therapy, and stringent glycemic control are key components of managing otomycosis in diabetic patients. Special attention should be given to those reporting severe pain or persistent discharge, as these may indicate complications like secondary bacterial infections or, in rare cases, malignant otitis externa.

The analysis of predisposing factors for otomycosis in patients with diabetes mellitus highlights that ear canal manipulation is the primary risk factor, reported by 52% of patients. In the study done by Sathish HS et al⁽⁴⁾ shows similar results which is 60% of the patients gave history of manipulation/trauma to the EAC with either stick, feather, metal picker, pin etc, In patients with diabetes, the skin of the external auditory canal is more susceptible to injury and infection due to impaired wound healing and immune function. Any disruption to the skin barrier provides an entry point for fungi to colonize, making manipulation a significant risk factor for otomycosis in this population. The presence of swimming as a minor factor suggests that some diabetic patients may be exposed to water frequently. Water exposure, particularly in environments where the ear canal remains moist for extended periods, creates an ideal breeding ground for fungal infections. In diabetic individuals, who are already at higher risk due to compromised immune defenses, swimming can exacerbate the likelihood of otomycosis. It is advisable to recommend preventive measures, such as the use of ear plugs or drying agents, for diabetic patients who frequently swim or are exposed to moisture.

The most frequently isolated fungus was *Aspergillus niger*, accounting for 44% of cases. Known for its association with external ear infections, it thrives in warm, humid environments. In diabetic patients, its ability to cause chronic infections necessitates careful management to prevent complications such as chronic otitis externa or invasive disease. Combined Military Hospital Attock⁽⁹⁾ study reported that *Aspergillus niger* was the most common isolate,

accounting for 52% of cases. The findings align with the current study in that *Aspergillus niger* is a predominant pathogen, The second most common isolate was *Aspergillus flavus* comprising 32% of cases. This species is particularly notable for its production of aflatoxins, which can exacerbate health issues in immunocompromised individuals. *Aspergillus fumigatus* identified in 16% of cases, this organism is associated with more severe forms of fungal infections. In the context of diabetic patients, *Aspergillus fumigatus* can lead to invasive disease, particularly in those with poor glycemic control. *Candida krusei* representing 4% of isolates, this yeast species is notable for its resistance to azole antifungals, making it a challenging pathogen to manage. *Scedosporium apiospermum* isolated in 2% of cases, this fungus can cause opportunistic infections, particularly in immunocompromised individuals like those with diabetes. *Scedosporium proliferans* representing 2% this organism is of concern for its opportunistic nature.

Limitations of the study:

This study is being done for otomycosis patients with diabetes mellitus, comparisons, management and outcome was not done.

Conclusion:

This population of otomycosis patients with diabetes mellitus is predominantly middle-aged to elderly, with a slight female predominance and a notable right-sided infection tendency. For diabetic patients, managing otomycosis requires a comprehensive approach focusing on meticulous ear hygiene, appropriate antifungal therapy, and stringent glycemic control to prevent recurrent infections and reduce the risk of complications. The high prevalence of *Aspergillus* species necessitates increased healthcare provider awareness for diagnosis and treatment, especially in immunocompromised patients. *Candida krusei* and *Scedosporium* growth were present, their detection which is rare is crucial to know their prevalence and treatment with resistance pattern. Further research is needed to understand environmental factors contributing to *Aspergillus* species' high prevalence and their antifungal resistance patterns.

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